

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Teacher's written and verbal corrective feedback on pupils' test anxiety

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Abstract

This study determined the effect of teacher's written and verbal corrective feedback on the test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils in Malipampang Elementary School, Malipampang, San Ildefonso, Bulacan during the School Year 2022 – 2023. With experimental mixed methods as research design and 93 Grades 5 pupils as respondents of the study, findings showed that the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions before subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes was above average. After conducting the experiment, the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback of checking the tests/quizzes was low. Meanwhile, the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions after subjecting them to traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes was described as below average. Based on the findings of the study, these conclusion was drawn: Written and verbal corrective feedback is an effective way of decreasing the test anxiety level of elementary school pupils.

Keywords: written; Verbal; Corrective Feedback; Test anxiety

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of feedback in connection to student learning. During the pandemic, students often receive only a grade on their final test, with no additional feedback. This lack of elaborated input can be attributed, at least in part, to a general trend, such as a growth in the total number of students and changes in educational policy. To accomplish learning objectives, students must have a clear knowledge of where they should be in relation to where they are at any given point in their learning process. They can identify any learning challenges and, based on feedback, take actions to reduce such limitations using this data. This lack of feedback has generated test anxiety in students who receive grades without knowing what they did incorrectly so they can improve it; without such feedback, students' test anxiety increases.

A lot of people have thought about and studied how emotions affect performance for a long time. One of the most studied emotions in relation to performance is anxiety, which is characterized by apprehension, worry, and a reduction in performance. Consistent reports place childhood anxiety disorders among the most common forms of mental illness, with a prevalence of up to 41%. Anxiety typically manifests itself in the form of physical symptoms when a person is placed in a position where his or her talents are being evaluated, for example. There is typically an unspoken fear of negative repercussions when facing an appraisal of aptitude. Anxiety, stress, and worry about performing poorly on a test are all commonly used synonyms for one another (von der Embse et al., 2017).

As a widespread response to stress, test anxiety is widely recognized as a prevalent form of anxiety among today's students. Anxiety over performing poorly on an exam or other forms of examination has been characterized as a complex of phenomenological, psychological, and behavioral responses accompanying fear about possible negative

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repercussions or failure (Duraku, 2017). Most analyses of test anxiety treat it as a two-factor phenomenon comprised of both emotional and mental aspects. The cognitive component of test anxiety includes students' fear and negative thoughts, self-criticism or concern about the negative repercussions of failure, which causes them to freeze up intellectually and forget what they need to know (Roos et al., 2020). A student's emotional state during an exam is characterized by physical manifestations of stress such as tense muscles, a racing heart, and sweaty palms (Duraku, 2017).

Self-report, behavioral measures like facial expression detection and classification, neuroimaging-based measures like functional magnetic resonance imaging, and measures of peripheral physiological systems are all viable ways to gauge test anxiety as the rate of heart beating or skin conductance (Avram et al., 2018). Numerous variables are thought to contribute to students' nervousness before exams. The set of elements influencing student performance and stress has been analyzed, and students' beliefs about their own knowledge and their capacity to learn more have been considered. Students' dissatisfaction with their academic performance, as seen by their complaints about not having enough time to study for tests and master course material, is one indicator of this issue.

It's been hypothesized that students' test-related anxieties shift as they progress through their college years. Data from a large body of studies show that first-year students are particularly at risk for developing a variety of psychological illnesses. Since the 1950s, studies on test anxiety have been conducted often. More than 2000 articles have been written on the topic of this negative emotion. Increased physiological arousal is a classic sign of test anxiety. It can be noninvasively evaluated by cardiovascular as in heart rate or electrodermal as in skin conductance techniques as in skin conductance response (Avram et al., 2018). Anxiety's physiological responses are notoriously tough to control. That being the case, physiological tests provide an objective method of gauging pupils' levels of arousal during exams. Nevertheless, self-report measures have been relied on extensively in the past to gauge exam anxiety, even though they may be swayed by factors like social desirability or subjective opinions (Roos, et al., 2020).

Anxiety before taking a test is more than a passing concern. For students, test anxiety can occur both in the lead-up to an exam, when nerves prevent enough study time and during the actual taking of the test itself (Quinn & Peters, 2017). Anxiety can cause test anxiety if it interferes with test-takers' ability to use their working memory for the test at hand.

Meanwhile, the term corrective feedback is used to describe comments on the appropriateness or correctness of a language learner's production or comprehension. One of the most active areas of study in the field of second language acquisition, corrective feedback has produced a large body of work in the last two and a half decades. Research on corrective feedback picked up speed after the release of two landmark studies on oral and written corrective feedback, respectively.

Written corrections to student writing that point out grammatical or stylistic problems in the L2 material are known as written corrective feedback. Most studies of written corrective feedback have focused on adult English as a second language (ESL) and English as a foreign language (EFL) learner, with the goal of determining whether or not this type of feedback aids in language acquisition as measured by the creation of more accurate texts. Most studies have looked at feedback in terms of which direction is most effective. The number of failed attempts that warrant written corrective feedback and the clarity of the feedback were also studied. Direct correction as providing amended version of the incorrect structure has been studied extensively in comparison to indirect correction as signaling that an error has occurred but not supplying the proper form (Storc, 2018). There has been scant investigation on whether it is more effective to provide general or error-specific feedback. More recent studies on written corrective feedback appear to be methodologically much more stringent, fixing problems with past written corrective feedback research.

A possible benefit of written corrective feedback on L2 writing accuracy. As evidence for the value of written corrective feedback in L2 learning has risen, so too have efforts to determine the most effective means of providing written corrective feedback and the level to which teachers should answer to written errors that is feedback scope. Although both approaches and scope are important in written corrective feedback, the quantity of written corrective feedback they should offer to students as whether to respond to all written errors or to selectively or concentrated ones is of immediate importance, especially for frontline teachers.

Both oral and written corrective feedback are included in this study to present a more complete picture of corrective feedback research, in contrast to previous evaluations that focused on either type of corrective feedback exclusively. Due to the similarities between the two corrective feedback types of study themes, the same framework may be utilized to arrange both sets of data.

It is in this premise that the researcher who is an elementary school teacher was inspired to conduct this study. With the hope that teacher's written and verbal corrective feedback could lessen or reduce the test anxiety of elementary school pupils, she was motivated to undertake this research.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

This study determined the effect of teacher's written and verbal corrective feedback on the test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils in Malipampang Elementary School, Malipampang, San Ildefonso, Bulacan during the School Year 2022 – 2023.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

- How may the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils before subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes be described in terms of:
 - Thoughts;
 - Off-task behaviors; and
 - Automatic reactions?
- How may the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes be described in terms of:
 - Thoughts;
 - Off-task behaviors; and
 - Automatic reactions?
- Is there a significant difference between the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils before and after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes?
- Is there a significant difference between the posttest mean score of Grade 5 pupils after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes?
- What are the views and insights of the respondents as regards the influence of written and verbal corrective feedback to their test anxiety?
- What program of activities can be crafted from the results of the study?

1.2 Hypotheses

The hypothesis that follows was tested in the study:

There is no significant difference between the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils before and after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes be described in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions.

1.3 Conceptual Framework

Students pursuing other disciplines typically experience test anxiety. Researchers from medicine, engineering, and physical therapy have investigated interventions to alleviate test anxiety (Quinn et al., 2017). Multiple factors are believed to influence test anxiety. Students' opinions of their knowledge and skills to improve their learning have been evaluated as part of the collection of variables impacting student performance and levels of stress. This element is expressed by students' complaints about not having enough time to study for tests or assimilate course material, as well as their dissatisfaction with their past academic achievement.

Since the 1950s, when some of the earliest and most significant research on test anxiety was published, it has influenced research and broadened our understanding of the role of emotion in performance. Despite decades of study establishing a connection between test anxiety and a variety of negative outcomes, test anxiety research dropped after the 1980s. In the current study, database searches of Psychinfo and ERIC produced 5% fewer results in the 1990s compared to the 1980s, with a further small decline in the early 2000s. Nonetheless, figures from 2010 to 2017 indicate a 31% rise in the amount of published research compared to the 1980s. In addition, the relationship between test anxiety and test performance has been the subject of substantial dispute in academic literature. As the concept approaches 70 years of research, the predictors, influencing variables, and theoretical knowledge of test anxiety have changed significantly (von der Embse et al., 2017).

Various theories of emotion suggest that there is a connection between self-reported emotional experiences and physiological responses, particularly in relation to test anxiety and other emotional connections. For instance, Roos et al. (2020) illustrates how the brain processes physiological cues, leading to the perception of associated emotions. However, the natural environment is also considered. Moreover, it is believed that internally generated input

contributes to cognition. Therefore, depending on the individual's attentional focus in body, world, or internal, the same physical reaction may result in more or less intense episodes of emotions in different people or circumstances. Numerous studies have elaborated on the concept that physical information is converted into emotional experiences. (Roos et al., 2020).

It is believed that test anxiety fluctuates during a university degree. Numerous studies indicate that the bulk of psychiatric disorders are frequent among first-year students. According to a study conducted by Cooke, Bewick, Barkham, Bradley, and Audin (2006 in Duraku, 2017), first-year students typically demonstrate psychological alterations, which frequently connect with financial difficulties and academic pressure. Furthermore, they discovered that students whose transition to university life is challenging have the most obvious stress symptoms (Duraku, 2017).

According to von der Embse, et al. (2017), the evolution of theoretical models of test anxiety during the past 50 years. The interference model of test anxiety explains low performance by identifying elements as emotion and worry that interfere with the process of information retention and application in testing settings. Shortly after the conception of this model, other theorists proposed a deficits model that attributes the occurrence and severity of test anxiety to deficiencies in the knowledge and skills as study skills, self-efficacy, motivation, testing strategies required to perform well in evaluative situations. Recent research reveals that neither of these models can explain the dynamic and highly variable nature of test anxiety. According to the attentional control theory, anxiety decreases performance due to a negative influence on attentional control, which includes shifting and suppressing. The transactional model of test anxiety incorporated previous models that incorporated interference and deficit theory, while viewing test anxiety as a cyclical or recursive phenomenon with test performance. Exam anxiety is related to both threat assessments and negative or positive evaluations, also the associated emotions. With their self-referential executive processing model to improve the transactional model by incorporating many anxiety-related effects on cognitive process. According to this paradigm, declarative and procedural self-knowledge determine executive processing, and self-referent processing occurs in response to dangerous external stimuli like dread of academic achievement, ultimately resulting in the manifestation of test anxiety (von der Embse et al., 2017).

Powell (2004 in Hieb, et al., 2015) determined that test anxiety contributed to the failure of 72 medical students on a licensure exam. These students participated in a therapy program for exam anxiety that included training in self-administered therapies such as progressive muscle relaxation. During treatment, 93% of the 72 participants passed the retake licensure exam; this was significantly higher than the average retake pass rate. Hieb, Lyle, Ralston, and Chariker (2015) examined a summer intervention program for the new engineering freshman who failed an algebra readiness exam. The intervention provides information on test-taking techniques in attempt to alleviate test anxiety. The algebra readiness examination results of students who participated in the intervention program were statistically significantly higher (Hieb et al., 2015).

According to Li and Vuono (2019), oral and written corrective feedback differ in numerous aspects. Oral corrective feedback involves the encoding and decoding of information presented aurally, whereas written corrective feedback is typically presented graphically. Oral corrective feedback is typically offered online during the development of a speech, whereas written corrective feedback is typically delivered after a written task has been completed. Oral corrective feedback is thus an integrated focus on form in which language forms are addressed in context and acquired knowledge is employed or proceduralized in immediate, subsequent production. It is not necessary to immediately develop the suggested structure after receiving written corrected input that has been decontextualized. Oral corrective feedback focuses primarily on language issues, which may or may not lead to communication failures, but written corrective feedback can address both language and content—the discourse and organizational components of writing. Oral corrective feedback can be either implicit or explicit, depending on whether learners are made aware of their inadequate speech performance. Written corrective feedback, on the other hand, is always explicit since students recognize the corrective objective regardless of delivery method (Li & Vuono, 2019). The difference between implicit and explicit corrective feedback therefore does not apply to written corrective feedback. Oral corrective feedback can be described as either providing input or prompting output, depending on whether the correct form is provided or withheld. The same differentiation applies to written corrective feedback, where the terms "direct" and "indirect" are used to indicate whether the feedback includes or lacks the necessary form. The research on written corrective feedback has also distinguished between focused and unfocused corrective feedback, which refers to whether corrective feedback targets one or multiple linguistic structures. Although this difference may also apply to oral corrective feedback, it appears to be more important in written corrective feedback, possibly because error correction in its whole is a common pedagogical strategy in L2 writing classes (Lee, 2018). In addition, while the teacher frequently delivers oral corrective feedback, both teacher and peer corrective feedback are prevalent in writing programs.

According to Mao and Lee (2020), several terms relating to written corrective feedback scope are used in the literature, including comprehensive, focused, and unfocused written corrective feedback. Complete written corrective feedback refers to the thorough correction of every error in student writing, which is a comprehensive method to error correction also some researchers have referred to it as unfocused written corrective feedback. Focused written corrective feedback, furthermore, adopts a more selective strategy and provides written corrective feedback on a limited number of error types. However, there is some ambiguity in the meanings of these two expressions. Complete written corrective feedback is sometimes known as unfocused written corrective feedback, but the latter term does not always refer to feedback on all errors.

In the case of written corrective feedback, tools might affect both the supply of feedback and the processing of feedback by learners. For instance, when written corrective feedback is offered through track adjustments and marginal remarks, we may observe an effect on the quantity and nature of feedback comments provided by the teacher, as well as on how learners engage with, comprehend, and apply the feedback (Khang & Han, 2015). Nonetheless, written feedback is more likely to be provided in the majority of L2 writing contexts.

It analyzed all of the feedback comments, including content and organization input, as well as the rhetorical styles of these comments as instructions and suggestions. Although the teacher feedback on all aspects of writing, the study found that a significant amount of the remarks was written corrective feedback and that the degree of directness of the criticism provided did not modify significantly over time (Lee et al., 2017). Due to the fact that the study only considered the nature of the feedback and did not examine the learner's response to the feedback, it is difficult to determine whether the learner's ability to use the feedback provided, including written corrective feedback, changed over time and, consequently, whether the feedback was indeed contingent.

From the theory, related studies and literature cited, presented and explained above, the researcher came up with the paradigm that will serve as guide in the conduct of the study.

Figure 1 Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1 shows that the independent variable is teacher's written and oral corrective feedback. This variable was hypothesized to influence (as implied by the arrowhead) the dependent variable which is the pupils' level of test anxiety.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study is beneficial and important in the educational arena. It will help the educators determine the effect of teacher's written and verbal corrective feedback on the test anxiety, and it will ultimately benefit the following:

Pupils. The outcomes of this study had the most impact, in terms of overall relevance, on the subject of lowering pupils' levels of test anxiety. Findings of this research will make the elementary school pupils feel at ease when they are taking tests or quizzes.

Teachers. The study is important for elementary school teachers because it will provide information and understanding about whether providing pupils with written or vocal remedial feedback is an effective approach for minimizing the amount of test anxiety that pupils experience. In addition, the findings of the study could provide the teachers with a foundation upon which to improve and expand their comments or feedback on pupils' tests/quizzes.

School Administrators. The findings can offer empirical data to school officials regarding the impact of providing pupils with written corrective feedback on reducing test anxiety. They may choose to incorporate the components that have been researched into their strategy for assisting teachers in improving their skills on how to make effective feedback or comments on pupils' work.

Future Researchers. Results of the study will serve a reference for researchers who have the same interests. The researcher ultimately believe that the findings of this study will help the future researchers to fully understand the impact of written corrective feedback on pupils' test anxiety.

1.5 Scope and Limitation of the Study

This research focused on determining the effect of teacher's written and verbal corrective feedback on the test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils in Malipampang Elementary School, Malipampang, San Ildefonso, Bulacan. This study was conducted in the third quarter of School Year 2022 – 2023.

To determine the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils before and after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes was described in terms of thoughts; off-task behaviors; and automatic reactions.

The researcher gave two written examinations to two sections of Grade 5. One section was the experimental group and the other was controlled group. The experimental group was used teacher's written and verbal corrective feedback on checking their written examinations. while the controlled group was still used the traditional way of checking their test.

1.6 Location of the Study

This study was conducted in Malipampang Elementary School, Malipampang, San Ildefonso, Bulacan. The main respondents of this study were the two heterogenous sections of Grade 5 under the supervision of their advisers.

Source: <https://www.google.com/maps/place/Malipampang+Elementary+School>

Figure 2 Map of Malipampang Elementary School, San Ildefonso South District

1.7 Definition of Terms

To shed the light in understanding, the following operational definitions are hereby presented.

- **Automatic reactions.** This refers to the actions done by the pupils that connotes a predictable response toward their tests.
- **Off-task behaviors.** This refers to the pupils' engagement in activities or conversations that are not part of the teacher-assigned instructional activity.
- **Test Anxiety.** This refers to a type of anxiety where pupils feel during their exam when they feel pressure to do well.
- **Thoughts.** This refers to the idea or thinking of the pupils about the tests they have to take.
- **Traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes.** This refers to checking the tests or quizzes without providing corrective feedback.
- **Verbal corrective feedback.** This refers to providing oral feedback to the pupils upon checking their tests or quizzes.
- **Written corrective feedback.** This refers to providing written feedback to the pupils upon checking their tests or quizzes

2 Material and methods

The information about the research and sampling procedures that was utilized by the researcher are provided in this chapter. The research design that was employed, as well as the data gathering techniques, and data analysis scheme were also discussed in this chapter.

2.1 Research Design

The experimental mixed methods methodology, combining quantitative measures of test anxiety with qualitative interviews to provide a more comprehensive understanding to determine the effects of written and verbal corrective feedback on pupils' test anxiety levels.

In the quantitative part of the study, the objective was to determine the effect of the teacher's written and verbal corrective feedback on pupils' test anxiety. To achieve this, the researchers distributed survey questionnaires to the participants before and after subjecting them to corrective feedback.

The participants were divided into two groups: the experimental group and the control group. The experimental group received both written and verbal corrective feedback from the teacher while their tests and quizzes were being checked. This feedback likely included specific reasons why they are wrong on certain questions. On the other hand, the control group received the traditional method of checking tests and quizzes, which may not have involved detailed feedback or comments.

Both groups administered the preliminary survey questionnaire before the corrective feedback intervention. Following the intervention, the same survey questionnaire was given as a final survey to measure any changes in test anxiety levels between the two groups.

The survey questionnaire was composed of three parts: thoughts, off-task behavior, and automatic reactions with eight item statements. This was rated at 5 – Very True of Me (VTM), 4 – True of Me (TM), 3 – Moderately True of Me (MTM), 2 – Slightly True of Me, and 1 – Not True of Me (NTM).

In the qualitative part of the study, the researchers aimed to gather the views and insights of the pupils regarding their feelings and perceptions of the teacher's use of written and verbal corrective feedback. They randomly selected ten pupils from the experimental group to participate in semi-structured interviews.

During the interviews, the researchers asked open-ended questions to elicit detailed responses from the participants. The questions may have focused on their feelings when the researcher provided written and verbal corrective feedback and if it helps to lower their test anxiety.

The semi-structured interviews provided an opportunity for the pupils to express their individual perspectives and share their unique insights.

Posttest was done to identify which group between controlled and experimental group has a lower level of test anxiety after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback.

2.2 Data Gathering Techniques

The researcher submitted a request for authorization to carry out the study in Malipampang, San Ildefonso, Bulacan to the Superintendent of the Schools Division of Bulacan. The researcher gave the pupils information about the experiment, and then they began participating in a series of tests that the researcher had prepared for them.

For the purpose of this research, both quantitative and qualitative data were obtained. The pupils' levels of test anxiety were measured using a survey questionnaire that was given to them. On the other hand, in order to collect qualitative data, we used interviews that were only semi-structured. During the interview, the researcher used the preliminary survey data as a basis for developing open-ended questions that she asked interview participants.

The only difference between the two groups is that the experimental group is provided with a written and verbal corrective feedback instruction technique while checking their test/quizzes, whilst the control group is not.

Table 1 presents the timetable of the study which guided and followed in the entire period of the experiment.

Table 1 Timetable of the Study

Duration (Week)	Topic/Content	Learning Competencies	Activities
Week 1	Orientation	To inform the pupils of their participation in the study.	Orientation
	Survey Questionnaire	To know the level of pupils' test anxiety before subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback.	Answering of Survey Questionnaires
Week 2	Administration of 1 st Written Examination	To implement the teachers' written and verbal corrective feedback.	Implementation of Teachers' written and verbal corrective feedback.
Week 3	Checking and feedbacking of 1 st Written Examination		
Week 4	Administration of 2 nd Written Examination		
Week 5	Checking and feedbacking of 2 nd Written Examination		
Week 6	Post-Test		
Week 6	Survey Questionnaire	To know the level of pupils' test anxiety after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback.	Answering of Survey Questionnaires
	Interview	To know the views and insights of the respondents as regards the influence of written and verbal corrective feedback to their test anxiety.	Interview

2.3 Sampling Procedures

Total population or universal sampling was utilized in the conduct of the study. All Grade 5 pupils handled by the researcher served as respondents of the study.

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents of the Study

Grade 5 Pupils	Total
Andres Bonifacio	47
Marcelo Del Pilar	46
Total	93

In the qualitative part of the study, the researchers aimed to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences and perspectives of the pupils who received written and verbal corrective feedback. The researcher randomly selected ten pupils to participate in the interview. These participants were then individually interviewed using a semi-structured interview.

The semi-structured interview allowed the researchers to have a flexible conversation with the pupils while ensuring that specific research questions were addressed. This type of interview has an open-ended discussion, enabling the participants to provide detailed responses and share their unique insights.

The qualitative findings obtained from these interviews would complement the quantitative data collected in the study. While the quantitative data may provide statistical evidence of the effectiveness of written and verbal corrective feedback, the qualitative data would offer detailed insights into the experiences, insights, perceptions, and thoughts of the pupils, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of the written and verbal corrected feedback they received.

Content analysis was used for the gathered qualitative data to determine the presence of words and concepts for better analysis of meanings and relationships of such certain words and concepts.

2.4 Data Analysis Scheme

After collecting all the quantitative data, these were organized, tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using some statistical tools.

Weighted mean was computed to describe the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils before and after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes.

t-test for correlated samples was utilized to determine if significant difference existed between the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils before and after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes.

3 Results

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data collected and the results of the statistical treatment employed in the study with the purpose of determining the effect of teacher's written and verbal corrective feedback on the test anxiety of public elementary school pupils.

3.1 The Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils before Subjecting them to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback and Traditional Way of Checking the Tests/Quizzes

Test anxiety among elementary school children is heightened due to the increase of high stakes testing the students are experiencing. Test anxiety is a condition where an individual experiences anxiety in a situation, such as an exam, and views it as threatening. Test anxiety is not an anxiety disorder, but rather an emotional reaction to the perceived threatening situation of taking a test; however, if elementary school pupils are not taught the skills needed to overcome the perceived threat, they are at risk of developing an anxiety disorder later in life.

The level of test anxiety among Grade 5 pupils before subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

3.1.1 Thoughts

Test anxiety is a psychological state where young children undergo intense distress and anxiety during testing situations. While it is common for people to experience some level of stress and anxiety before and during exams, test anxiety goes beyond that and can negatively impact learning and test performance.

Table 3 presents the assessments of the Grade 5 pupils as regards the level of their test anxiety before they were exposed to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes in terms of thoughts.

Table 3 Mean Scores for the Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils before Subjecting them to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback and Traditional Way of Checking the Tests/Quizzes in terms of Thoughts

Item Statement <i>While taking a test/exam...</i>	Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback		Traditional Way of Checking	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
1. I think I am going to get a bad grade.	4.15	TM	4.16	TM
2. I think about what will happen if I fail.	4.09	TM	4.07	TM

3. I worry about what my parents will say.	4.00	TM	4.02	TM
4. I worry about failing.	4.26	VT	4.17	TM
5. I worry about doing something wrong.	4.22	VT	4.21	VT
6. I think about what my grade will be.	4.15	TM	4.18	TM
7. I think most of my answers are wrong.	3.98	TM	4.01	TM
8. I worry about how hard the test is.	4.07	TM	4.16	TM
Overall Mean	4.11	TM	4.12	TM
t-value	-0.169 ns			
p-value	0.868			

Note: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Very True of Me (VT) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: True of Me (TM) – Above Average; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately True of Me (MT) – Average; 1.81 – 2.60: Slightly True of Me (ST) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Not True of Me (NT) – Low

It can be noted from the table that the group who was exposed to written and verbal corrective feedback gave their highest assessment to item “While taking a test/exam, I worry about failing” with a computed weighted mean of 4.26 and verbal description of “very true of me”. On the other hand, item “While taking a test/exam, I think most of my answers are wrong” received the lowest computed weighted mean of 3.98 with a verbal description of “true of me”. The overall mean was registered at 4.11 which is also verbally described as “true of me”. These results imply that before exposing the respondents to written and verbal corrective feedback, the level of their test anxiety was “above average”.

On the control group (traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes), the highest computed weighted mean of 4.21 was registered in item “While taking a test/exam, I worry about doing something wrong” which is verbally described as “very true of me”. On the other hand, item “While taking a test/exam, I think most of my answers are wrong” yielded the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.01 with a verbal interpretation of “true of me”. The overall mean was calculated at 4.12 with a verbal interpretation of “true of me.”

Further perusal of the same table reveals that when the level of test anxiety of the two groups of respondents before conducting the experiment was the same. This same level of test anxiety is manifested by the t-value of -0.169 which is interpreted as not significant as implied by the probability value of 0.868 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance.

These results imply that before conducting the experiment, the Grade 5 pupils exhibit negative thinking before taking tests/quizzes, which can have various negative consequences on their performance and motivation. Negative thinking can lose their motivation to pass their exams and think negative including parents' opinions regarding their low scores and some pupils may even think they have answered incorrectly before their answers have been checked which may lead to lower scores or grades. The pupils tend to focus on potential failures, doubts, and unfavorable outcomes rather than adopting a positive and confident mindset. Furthermore, by focusing on potential failures and expecting poor outcomes, students may undermine their own abilities and limit their potential for success.

According to (Yusefzadeh et al, 2019) the students who suffer from negative thoughts frequently experienced distraction in exams and problems. Several factors affect positive effect of critical thinking and active learning strategies that could enhance critical thinking and positive thoughts to encourage the students to do not fear their test.

3.1.2 Off-Task Behaviors

Off-task behavior is an indicator that students' attention is not focused on the instructional activity. Off-task behavior is a serious challenge educators face. In fact, off-task behavior has been identified as one of the most common reasons for student referrals. Although completely eliminating off-task behavior may not be a practical expectation, reducing its frequency is a significant objective due to the difficulties it poses for classroom management and the potential impact on academic achievement.

Table 4 Mean Scores for the Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils before Subjecting them to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback and Traditional Way of Checking the Tests/Quizzes in terms of Off-Task Behaviors

Item Statement <i>While taking a test/exam...</i>	Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback		Traditional Way of Checking	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
1. I look around the room.	4.20	TM	4.13	TM
2. I look at my classmates.	4.20	TM	4.23	VT
3. I stare.	4.07	TM	4.26	VT
4. I always check the time.	4.22	VT	4.02	TM
5. I find it hard to sit still.	4.13	TM	4.13	TM
6. I tap my feet.	3.98	TM	3.98	TM
7. I play with my pencil/ballpen.	4.35	VT	4.34	VT
8. I try to finish up fast.	4.17	TM	4.17	TM
Overall Mean	4.16	TM	4.16	TM

Note: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Very True of Me (VT) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: True of Me (TM) – Above Average; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately True of Me (MT) – Average; 1.81 – 2.60: Slightly True of Me (ST) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Not True of Me (NT) – Low

Table 4 exhibits the assessments of the Grade 5 pupils as regards the level of their test anxiety before they were exposed to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes in terms of off-task behaviors.

It can be noted from the table that both groups of respondents gave their highest assessments to item “While taking a test/exam I play with my pencil/ballpen” with a computed weighted mean of 4.35 (very true of me) from the experimental group and 4.34 (very true of me) from the control group. Meanwhile, these groups of respondents gave their lowest assessments to item “While taking a test/exam I tap my feet” with a computed weighted mean of 3.98 which is verbally described as “true of me.” The computed overall mean of 4.16 (true of me) was computed for the two groups of respondents.

These results imply that the control and experimental groups had the same level of test anxiety where off-task behavior is concerned. Both groups have the same ways of responding with their actions that affect the behaviors while taking exam/quizzes. There are actions that made these groups similar before subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking.

(Godwin, 2020) agreed that off-task behavior caused serious problems when it comes of taking exams/quizzes that have an impact to learners’ academic achievement. However, students’ inattentiveness has been found to be the biggest factor that accounts for loss of learning and focus.

3.1.3 Automatic Reactions

For many students, automatic reactions can be a combination of things. Similar to other scenarios involving performance anxiety, test anxiety can manifest in physical symptoms such as butterflies in the stomach, a stomachache, or a headache. Individuals may also experience trembling, sweating, or a rapid heartbeat while waiting for the test to be distributed. In severe cases of test anxiety, a student may even feel lightheaded or nauseous to the point of potentially fainting or vomiting. Table 5 summarizes the assessments of the Grade 5 pupils with regard to the level of their test anxiety before exposing them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes in terms of automatic reactions.

Table 5 Mean Scores for the Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils before Subjecting them to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback and Traditional Way of Checking the Tests/Quizzes in terms of Automatic Reactions

Item Statement <i>While taking a test/exam...</i>	Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback		Traditional Way of Checking	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
1. I feel nervous.	4.36	VT	4.30	VT
2. My heart beats fast.	4.26	VT	4.15	TM
3. I feel scared.	4.00	TM	4.23	VT
4. My head hurts.	4.24	VT	4.19	TM
5. My face feels hot.	4.30	VT	4.34	VT
6. I feel warm.	4.26	VT	4.13	TM
7. My hand shakes.	3.91	TM	4.04	TM
8. I always feel that I have to go to the bathroom.	4.13	TM	4.22	VT
Overall Mean	4.18	TM	4.20	TM
t-value	-0.273 ns			
p-value	0.789			

Note: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Very True of Me (VT) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: True of Me (TM) – Above Average; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately True of Me (MT) – Average; 1.81 – 2.60: Slightly True of Me (ST) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Not True of Me (NT) – Low

It can be seen from the table that item “While taking a test/exam I feel nervous” received the highest computed weighted mean of 4.36 from the experimental group and 4.30 from the control group, both of which are verbally described as “very true of me.” On the other hand, item “While taking a test/exam my handshakes” yielded the lowest computed weighted mean scores of 3.91 for the experimental group and 4.04 for the control group, both of which are verbally described as “true of me.” The overall mean of 4.18 (true of me) was registered for the experimental group and 4.20 (true of me) for the control group.

These results imply that before conducting the experiment, Grade 5 pupils had the same level of test anxiety when it comes to automatic reactions that they feel and observed on their body during test/quizzes.

In accordance with the present findings of (Aydin, 2021), it noted that the scale consisted of sub-factors such as test irrelevant thinking, worry, tensions and bodily reactions will be the reason why learners have fears in taking exam/quizzes.

3.2 The Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils after Subjecting them to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback and Traditional Way of Checking the Tests/Quizzes

After exposing the experimental group to written and verbal corrective feedback and the control group to traditional way of checking tests/quizzes, the same instrument was administered, and results are shown in Tables 6 to 8.

3.2.1 Thoughts

The assessments of the control and experimental groups as regards the level of their anxiety in terms of thoughts after exposing them to written and verbal corrective feedback and to traditional way of checking tests/quizzes are manifested in Table 6.

Table 6 Mean Scores for the Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils after Subjecting them to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback and Traditional Way of Checking the Tests/Quizzes in terms of Thoughts

Item Statement <i>While taking a test/exam...</i>	Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback		Traditional Way of Checking	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
1. I think I am going to get a bad grade.	1.07	NT	2.41	ST
2. I think about what will happen if I fail.	1.22	NT	2.59	ST
3. I worry about what my parents will say.	1.37	NT	2.60	ST
4. I worry about failing.	1.07	NT	2.56	ST
5. I worry about doing something wrong.	1.15	NT	2.49	ST
6. I think about what my grade will be.	1.17	NT	2.48	ST
7. I think most of my answers are wrong.	1.02	NT	2.34	ST
8. I worry about how hard the test is.	1.17	NT	2.48	ST
Overall Mean	1.15	NT	2.49	ST

Note: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Very True of Me (VT) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: True of Me (TM) – Above Average; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately True of Me (MT) – Average; 1.81 – 2.60: Slightly True of Me (ST) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Not True of Me (NT) – Low

It can be gleaned from the table that item “While taking a test/exam I worry about what my parents will say” received the highest computed weighted mean of 1.37 from the experimental group and 2.60 from the control group. On the other hand, item “While taking a test/exam I think most of my answers are wrong” garnered the lowest computed weighted mean scores of 1.02 for the experimental group and 2.34 for the control group. All items indicated in the table for the assessments of the experimental group including the computed overall mean of 1.15 registered the same verbal interpretation of “not true of me.” The same with the control group, all items including the computed overall mean of 2.49 obtained the same verbal description of “slightly true of me.”

These results imply that written and corrective feedback helps to improve the thoughts of learners because of giving feedback. It helps them increase their motivation, focus and drive to think positively even if they passed or failed the test.

(Sheen et.al, 2021) stated that corrective feedback and learners’ uptake across instructional setting. It leads learners to have positive thoughts while taking exams because of the purposive effects of giving feedback that helps them to motivate and lessen their test anxiety in regards of their thoughts and mind concepts about what would happen if they failed the test.

In the conducted interview with the experimental group of pupils, they were asked about how they felt when they provided written and corrective feedback. Some respondents responded, “*It give us positive thoughts that we can pass the exam.*” These respondents showed that their thoughts and ways of thinking about their exam have been improved after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the test/quizzes.

3.2.2 Off-Task Behaviors

The assessments of the control and experimental groups with regard to the level of their anxiety in terms of off-task behaviors after exposing them to written and verbal corrective feedback and to traditional way of checking tests/quizzes are presented in Table 7.

Table 7 Mean Scores for the Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils after Subjecting them to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback and Traditional Way of Checking the Tests/Quizzes in terms of Off-Task Behaviors

Item Statement <i>While taking a test/exam...</i>	Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback		Traditional Way of Checking	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
1. I look around the room.	1.48	NT	2.16	ST
2. I look at my classmates.	1.43	NT	2.48	ST
3. I stare.	1.09	NT	2.01	ST
4. I always check the time.	1.15	NT	1.89	ST
5. I find it hard to sit still.	1.07	NT	2.36	ST
6. I tap my feet.	1.13	NT	1.98	ST
7. I play with my pencil/ballpen.	1.28	NT	2.13	ST
8. I try to finish up fast.	1.02	NT	2.03	ST
Overall Mean	1.21	NT	2.13	ST

Note: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Very True of Me (VT) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: True of Me (TM) – Above Average; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately True of Me (MT) – Average; 1.81 – 2.60: Slightly True of Me (ST) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Not True of Me (NT) – Low

It can be examined from the table that in the experimental group, items “While taking a test/exam I look around the room” and “While taking a test/exam I try to finish up fast” received the highest and lowest computed weighted mean scores of 1.48 and 1.02, respectively. Interestingly, all items indicated in the table received the lowest verbal interpretation of “not true of me.”

Further examination of the same table reveals that in the control group, items “While taking a test/exam I look at my classmates” and “While taking a test/exam I always check the time” yielded the highest and lowest computed weighted mean scores of 2.48 and 1.89, respectively. Apparently, all items indicated in the table received the lowest verbal interpretation of “slightly true of me.”

The result implies that off-task behavior while taking exam/quizzes was reduce both in control and experimental group. It gives further perusal that written and corrective feedback lessen the off-task behavior of learners while taking a test or exam.

In line with current findings, (Drown et.al, 2021) stated that giving feedback is an essential construct for learning and instructions, it is also an understanding of the conditions for effective giving of feedback, that can facilitate off-task behavior and can reduce unintended actions that can be hindrance of effective test taking and learning process.

In the conducted interview with the experimental group, they were asked about how they felt when they provided written and corrective feedback. Some respondents replied that “*It lessen our unwanted actions and behavior while taking exam because we can actually understand why we are correct or wronged on the test item.*” These respondents showed that their off-task behavior have been less after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the test/quizzes.

3.2.3 Automatic Reactions

The assessments of the control and experimental groups regarding the level of their anxiety in terms of automatic reactions after exposing them to written and verbal corrective feedback and to traditional way of checking tests/quizzes are presented in Table 8.

Table 8 Mean Scores for the Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils after Subjecting them to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback and Traditional Way of Checking the Tests/Quizzes in terms of Automatic Reactions

Item Statement <i>While taking a test/exam...</i>	Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback		Traditional Way of Checking	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
1. I feel nervous.	1.00	NT	2.28	ST
2. My heart beats fast.	1.15	NT	2.18	ST
3. I feel scared.	1.07	NT	2.01	ST
4. My head hurts.	1.11	NT	1.98	ST
5. My face feels hot.	1.09	NT	2.26	ST
6. I feel warm.	1.11	NT	1.88	ST
7. My hand shakes.	1.04	NT	2.09	ST
8. I always feel that I have to go to the bathroom.	1.11	NT	2.19	ST
Overall Mean	1.08	NT	2.11	ST

Note: Scale: Verbal Description; 4.21 – 5.00: Very True of Me (VT) – High; 3.41 – 4.20: True of Me (TM) – Above Average; 2.61 – 3.40: Moderately True of Me (MT) – Average; 1.81 – 2.60: Slightly True of Me (ST) – Below Average; 1.00 – 1.80: Not True of Me (NT) – Low

It can be observed from the table that after exposing the Grade 5 pupils to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback all items indicated in the table received the lowest verbal description of “not true of me.” A closer look at the table reveals that item “While taking a test/exam my heart beats fast” received the highest computed weighted mean of 1.15 while item “While taking a test/exam I feel nervous” got the lowest computed weighted mean of 1.00. The overall mean was registered at 1.08.

Further observation of the same table shows that in the control group, item “While taking a test/exam I feel nervous” received the highest computed weighted mean of 2.28 while item “While taking a test/exam I feel warm” got the lowest computed weighted mean of 1.88. All items indicated in the table including the computed overall mean of 2.11 registered the same verbal description of “slightly true of me.”

These results imply that when the grade 5 pupils were exposed to written and verbal corrective feedback, the level of their anxiety in taking tests/quizzes decreased which may result to higher scores. This will make the Grade 5 pupils perform well in their exams while removing their automatic reactions that become a hindrance after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback.

In light with the current findings of the study (Havrenek, 2020) affirms that the corrective feedback causes learners to do better in the test, their average success improves. Corrective feedback recognized the elimination of reactions for further test experience. This also provided empirical support for learners who wish to be corrected by framing realistic questions that will lessen their automatic responses.

In the conducted interview with the randomly selected pupils. They were asked if written and verbal corrective helps them to lower their test anxiety. Some respondents answered, “*It lessen the feeling of nervousness and anxiety during test/quizzes.*” These showed that their level of test anxiety has been lessened after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the test/quizzes.

3.3 The Difference between the Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils

In this part of the study, Table 9 presents the results of the t-test analysis which was performed to determine if significant difference existed between the level of test anxiety of grade 5 pupils before and after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes.

Table 9 Results of the t-test Analysis on the Difference between the Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils before and after Subjecting them to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback and Traditional Way of Checking the Tests/Quizzes

Item	Mean		Mean Diff.	t-value	p-value
	Before	After			
<i>Traditional Thoughts</i>	4.12	2.49	1.63	10.718**	0.000
off-task behaviors	4.16	2.13	2.03	24.550**	0.000
automatic reactions	4.20	2.11	2.09	36.875**	0.000
<i>Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback thoughts</i>	4.11	1.15	2.96	56.778**	0.000
off-task behaviors	4.16	1.21	2.95	41.088**	0.000
automatic reactions	4.18	1.08	3.1	54.045**	0.000

Note: ** = Highly Significant ($p \leq 0.01$)

It can be noted from the table that highly significant difference was found between the level of test anxiety in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors, and automatic reactions before and after subjecting the Grade 5 pupils to traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes. This highly significant difference was brought about by the fact that the computed probability value of 0.000 for these variables is smaller than the 0.01 significance level. These results disclose that the level of anxiety of the Grade 5 pupils in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions decreases after conducting the experiment. These changes may due to the fact that as time goes on, the pupils became familiar with the teacher as well as with the styles of exam/quizzes administered by the researcher. Further, the Grade 5 pupils became more comfortable in taking the tests/quizzes which subsequently contributed to lessen the level of their anxiety.

A closer look at the table reveals that highly significant difference was found between the level of test anxiety in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions when the Grade 5 pupils before and after exposing them to written and verbal corrective feedback. This highly significant difference is manifested by the computed probability value of 0.000 which is smaller than the 0.01 significance level. This shows that the level of test anxiety level of the Grade 5 pupils decreases after exposing them to verbal corrective feedback ways of checking the tests/quizzes.

In conformity with the findings of the present study, Alazemi (2022) conducted research which aimed to investigate the effectiveness of teachers' written and verbal corrective feedback during the formative assessment on learners' academic anxiety, academic performance, and attitude toward learning. The study used a convenience sampling method and included 76 students who were divided into an experimental group (EG) and a control group (CG). The EG received written and verbal corrective feedback, while the CG was taught using traditional methods. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, the results indicated that the teachers' written and verbal corrective feedback during the experiment positively affected the experimental language learners' AP. In addition, the results showed that teachers' written and verbal corrective feedback significantly decreased the EG's level of anxiety. As regards to the learners' attitude towards learning (ATL), the results showed that there was a significant change in the pre-test and post-test due to the feedback received from the teacher, which means that learners' ATL enhanced remarkably. Considering the results of this study, a number of conclusions are drawn, and several implications are put forward.

Table 10 reveals the results of the t-test analysis which was performed to determine if significant difference existed between posttests mean scores for written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests, quizzes and exams. This was done to find out which group (control or experimental) has less level of test anxiety after performing the experiment.

As revealed in the table, highly significant difference was found between the posttest mean scores of the control or experimental groups after exposing them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes. Results showed that the group who was exposed to written and verbal corrective feedback had a lower level of test anxiety as compared to the group who was exposed to traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes.

Results imply that written and verbal corrective feedback is an effective strategy to lower (if not totally eliminate) the level of test anxiety among elementary school pupils.

Table 10 Results of the t-test Analysis on the Difference between the Level of Test Anxiety of Grade 5 Pupils after Subjecting them to Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback and Traditional Way of Checking the Tests/Quizzes

Item	Mean for Posttests		Mean Diff.	t-value	p-value
	WVCF	Trad			
Thoughts	1.15	2.49	-1.34	-8.671**	0.000
off-task behaviors	1.21	2.13	-0.92	-9.906**	0.000
automatic reactions	1.08	2.11	-1.03	-19.923**	0.000

Note: ** = Highly Significant ($p \leq 0.01$), Trad = Traditional way, WVCF = Written and Verbal Corrective Feedback

In accordance to the present findings, Hunnikin et al., (2022) reported that written and corrective feedback provided immediately to the student that causes the student to have a positive attitude towards continuous learning and less test anxiety during tests or exams. The final result of this study was that students who received immediate written and corrective feedback reached better academic performance (Hoorens et al., 2021; Mainhard et al., 2018). The results of studies have also shown that teachers' feedback has a positive effect on improving the level of emotions of students' academic achievement. Another consequence of their research was that feedback is one of teachers' most important personality and behavioral characteristics in the classroom. Samuel (2021), in her study on factors influencing the academic resilience of high school students, the researcher concluded that several variables played significant roles. These variables included academic optimism, parental support, corrective and constructive teacher feedback, self-confidence, positive thinking, and high motivation. The study found that these factors were important predictors of both academic resilience and academic performance among high school students.

3.4 Program of Activities Crated from the Results of the Study

Results of the study revealed that written and corrective feedback is an effective way of reducing the level of test anxiety among Grade 5 pupils. Hence, the researcher proposed a plan to share the results of the present study to her colleagues so that they can also apply this in their own classes.

Table 11 Proposed Program of Activities to Lower the Level of Pupils' Test Anxiety

Objectives	Action	Timeline	Persons Involved	Expected Outcome
To make other teachers aware of the importance of using written and verbal corrective feedback.	Conduct a meeting with other teachers	1 st Quarter of S.Y. 2022-2023	Researcher, Principal, Teachers	At the end of the meeting, teachers are expected to apply written and verbal corrective feedback in their own classes.
To reduce the level of test anxiety among pupils.	Introduce relaxation techniques, such as deep breathing exercises and muscle relaxation, during classroom sessions.	1st Quarter of S.Y. 2022-2023	Researcher, Principal, Teachers	Enhanced ability of pupils to apply relaxation techniques during test situations.
To create a supportive and positive learning environment that reduces test anxiety among pupils.	Provide constructive feedback that focuses on improvement rather than grades.	Beginning of the academic year	Researcher, Teachers	Decreased test anxiety due to a focus on growth and progress rather than solely on outcomes.
Implement effective study and test preparation strategies.	Teach students effective study techniques, such as creating study schedules, breaking down material into manageable task, and practicing active learning strategies.	Beginning of the academic year	Researcher, Teachers	Reduced anxiety related to feeling unprepared or uncertain about test content or format.

4 Discussion

This study determined the effect of teacher's written and verbal corrective feedback on the test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils in Malipampang Elementary School, Malipampang, San Ildefonso, Bulacan during the School Year 2022 – 2023.

Using the procedures described in the preceding chapter, the answers to the problems raised in this study were ascertained and summarized as follows: Findings revealed that the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions before subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes was above average.

After conducting the experiment, the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions after subjecting them to written and verbal corrective feedback of checking the tests/quizzes was low.

Meanwhile, the level of test anxiety of Grade 5 pupils in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions after subjecting them to traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes was described as below average.

Highly significant difference was found between the level of test anxiety in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions before and after subjecting the Grade 5 pupils to traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes.

Likewise, highly significant difference was found between the level of test anxiety in terms of thoughts, off-task behaviors and automatic reactions when the Grade 5 pupils before and after exposing them to written and verbal corrective feedback.

Similarly, highly significant difference was found between the posttest mean scores of the control or experimental groups after exposing them to written and verbal corrective feedback and traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes. Results showed that the group who was exposed to written and verbal corrective feedback has a lower level of test anxiety as compared to the group who was exposed to traditional way of checking the tests/quizzes.

5 Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Written and verbal corrective feedback is an effective way of decreasing the test anxiety level of elementary school pupils.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

- The school may conduct the program of activities proposed by the researcher.
 - Inclusion of grades as another variable for the study may consider.
 - The teacher may use written and verbal corrective feedback in checking test/quizzes in all learning areas.
 - The teacher may use written and verbal corrective feedback for Performance Type of Test and other experimental learning assessment in order to enhance the motivation and learning outcomes of pupils.
 - For future researchers, further research along this line could be conducted. The same study may be conducted by including one specific subject as variable of the study.
-

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

All authors contributed positively to the writing of this manuscript and there no conflict of interest as agreed to the content of this research. The researchers have no affiliations with or involvement in any organizations, or entities with any financial, and non-financial interest in the subject matter, materials, and methods discussed in this study.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individuals respondents included in the study.

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